

LEARNING LOOPS IN THE PUBLIC REALM

WP3. Co-creation framework and platform

T3.1. Development of the methodology for the co-design of alternatives

Deliverable D 3.1

Guidelines for the co-design of alternatives

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

These guidelines on co-design tools are a deliverable within LOOPER (Learning Loops in the Public Realm), a JPI Europe funded research project with Living Labs in Brussels, Manchester and Verona. The aim of this project is to build a participatory co-creation methodology and platform to demonstrate 'learning loops', bringing together citizens, stakeholders and policy-makers to iteratively learn how to address urban challenges such as road safety, traffic calming, air and noise pollution.

This deliverable provides an analysis and evaluation of online, digital and face-to-face tools that can enhance a co-creation process in Living Labs, and in particular the co-design stage. These guidelines provide both an overview on the breadth of tools available and 21 in-depth factsheets on tools that are promising for LOOPER. As the Living Labs become more concrete, resources can be chosen according to the evolving needs.

Methodologically, this review is based on an online scoping of potential tools using a broad set of keywords. Selection of tools may therefore be impacted by the subjective bias of the authors and dependent of a given tool's publicity online. A table with all reviewed tools can be found in the appendix.

For face-to-face interaction, a wealth of handbooks has been found. A good start are the introductory chapters of the [Participatory Methods Toolkit](#) by the King Bauduin Foundation, followed by a look-over of the 23 methods in the [Collective Action Toolkit](#) by Frog Design or the [bootcamp bootleg](#) of Stanford's d-school. The urb@exp [LAB kit](#) can be employed at the inception of the Living Lab or if direction and structure is lacking during its implementation. When reaching the creative stage, Stanford's [virtual crash course](#) can be a great engaging 90-minute activity for participants to provide them with creative energy and methods to tackle their problems.

Online co-creation tools have a great variety of functionalities that can be incorporated into online co-creation platforms. As communication is of vital importance in the co-creation process, a co-creation platform should always include a messaging and spatial commenting functionality. Which other tools are most useful depends on the needs of a platform, the technical knowledge of participants and practitioners, and available financial resources. For ready-to-use co-creation solutions, take a look at TransformCity and Citizenlab.

2 INTRODUCTION

When setting up their own participatory process, researchers and citizens are confronted with a wide array of online and offline tools targeted towards facilitating the co-creation of solutions to urban conflicts and problems. With such a multitude of techniques available and approaches differing across countries and academic fields, how can one make an informed choice?

This deliverable summarizes the results of a methods review undertaken within the LOOPER project and aims to provide useful resources as well as a broad overview of the current of co-creation and collaborative planning methods landscapes.

This deliverable aims to answer the following research questions:

- What is co-design and what are its integral components and principles?
- How does co-design link with other stages of the co-creation process as defined in LOOPER?
- What tools can be employed in the LOOPER Living Labs to facilitate co-design?
- Looking across disciplines, what tools can aid co-design?
- Which aspects should be taken into consideration when choosing a specific tool for a LOOPER Living Lab?

The guidelines in this deliverable first conceptualize the terms co-creation and co-design and their process steps (section 5). The methodology chapter (section 6) describes the review process. In the subsequent debrief (section 7), we provide an overview of identified features and propose two ways of grouping tools. This is followed by more detailed sections on potential audiences (7.1), different types of face-to-face tools (7.2), online tools (7.3) and digital tools (7.4). We then present the results of the

tool review, with dedicated factsheets for the 21 most promising tools identified. Lastly, conclusions are drawn for potentials tools for the LOOPER project.

3 HOW TO USE THESE GUIDELINES

3.1 For whom are these guidelines?

These guidelines can be used by anyone who has the responsibility to set up a framework for a participatory process and is looking for useful resources and who would like to make informed choices on the methods and approaches to be employed in their participatory process. The potential audience therefore may include researchers, city officials, urban planners, and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) or citizens who are organizing a participatory initiative.

These guidelines have been compiled for three specific Urban Living Labs on mobility and public space related issues in urban areas (e.g. street safety and air quality). However, the reviewed methods can be employed in many circumstances and participatory processes other than Living Labs.

3.2 How to use these guidelines?

The results section of this deliverable consists of four parts:

- 1. Debrief of identified tool features**

The reviewed tools have been classified and grouped. A first section details these classifications, provides the reader an overview of the variety of tools available and allows for a better understanding of the factsheets and terms used in them.

- 2. Discussion of further types of tools**

We give an overview of facilitator trainings, digital software, and plug-ins for programming one's own participatory platform.

- 3. Factsheets**

The factsheets give a more detailed review of the most promising tools in the areas of face-to-face workshop facilitation and online participatory discourse.

- 4. Review table**

All 69 identified tools and their rudimentary reviews are available in a table in the appendix.

Large parts of this deliverable are to be integrated into the online LOOPER platform where they can be read more interactively, non-linearly, and where reviewed tools can be filtered by the reader's preferred features. The debrief of the identified tool features may then be presented to the website user as shortly described categories he or she can choose from before being forwarded to a filtered list of applicable factsheets or the respective section on training, plug-ins or digital support systems. In addition, visitors of the LOOPER platform will then be provided with the concrete example how a given tool was used in one of the LOOPER Living Labs.

4 THE LOOPER PROJECT CONTEXT

These guidelines are a deliverable within LOOPER (Learning Loops in the Public Realm), a JPI Europe funded research project with Living Labs in Brussels, Manchester and Verona. The aim of this project is to build a participatory co-creation methodology and platform to demonstrate 'learning loops', bringing together citizens, stakeholders and policy-makers to iteratively learn how to address urban challenges such as road safety, traffic calming, air and noise pollution.

4.1 Connection with other deliverables

The underlying concepts like Living Labs and co-creation as well as the focus on learning loops which underpin the LOOPER methodology are detailed in deliverable D4.1. Deliverable 3.2 on the inclusion of hard-to-reach groups in the Living Lab process will provide further guidance on how to choose methods that are inclusive and choose tools in a way that most people can be accommodated. Lastly, a detailed

choice of methods with concrete examples and reasoning behind a choice of methods for each Living Labs will be laid out in D5.1, 6.1 and 7.1. This deliverable D3.1 informs these implementation plans by providing an overview of resources from which to choose.

5 CONCEPTUAL APPROACH

5.1 What is Co-Creation and Co-Design?

Co-creation is an umbrella term for a wide range of participatory and open-design processes. It is an approach to creative practice by moving beyond consultation towards collaboration between the citizens impacted by an issue. It puts the user and citizen as the 'expert' of their own life at centre stage of the design process. Co-design is usually facilitated by a professional, who might choose a certain approach, and within that various methods or tools to spark creativity and keep a process of reiterative questioning, refining, reflection going. Scenario or prototypes can be built and reviewed. While co-design as an approach asserts users to be capable experts of their own experiences, they must still be supported through tools that allow them to express themselves (Chrisholm, 2017).

In the LOOPER project, we define co-creation as the overall joint process of tackling an issue. Co-Design is understood as the process of designing a solution from an initial idea to a product ready to be implemented. It is therefore a sub-section of co-creation.

5.2 What about the "Co" in Co-Design?

The "Co" in Co-Design may stand for community or for cooperation. What is at the core is a "togetherness" when designing, as it is a participatory approach. Arnstein's ladder of citizen participation (1969) highlights how participation, and therefore also Co-Creation and Co-Design processes, should be reviewed in view of the real power that is transferred to citizens. Any tool discussed here does not make a process co-creative simply by being utilised. Instead, this is determined by the empowerment of citizens and whether in reality joint decision-making between all involved parties takes place.

The objectives behind conducting co-design need to be critically evaluated before setting up the process. If power is unevenly distributed, such restraints to the process should be acknowledged and worked with. A good starting point for reflections on the objectives behind a given participatory process are the introductory chapters in the "[Participatory Methods Toolbox](#)" (Elliott et al., 2005)

Categorisation of Objectives for Conducting Participatory Methods

The poles of the Aspiration/Motivation axis are defined as 'Democratisation' versus 'Advising', while the Targeted Output axis is divided into 'Mapping out Diversity' versus 'Reaching Consensus'. Each of these poles is defined as follows:

Axis 1: Aspiration/Motivation

Democratisation: The purpose of using the method is to enable participants to employ their own knowledge to create options for tackling (policy) issues that directly concern them. The output has weight in the decision-making process and can be binding.

Advising: The purpose of using the method is to reveal stakeholders' knowledge, values and ideas that are relevant to the process of decision-making. The output is used as input to the decision-support process.

Axis 2: Targeted Output

Mapping Out Diversity: The purpose is to generate a spectrum of options and information and to enable a group to disclose information (making tacit knowledge explicit) or test alternative strategies in a permissive environment.

Reaching Consensus: The purpose is to enable a group to reach a single informed decision on an issue.

Figure 1: Objectives for conducting participatory methods
(Source: "Participatory Methods Toolkit" Elliott et al., 2005)

5.3 What about the "Design" in Co-Design?

Next to being truly participatory and aiming for consensus within diverse groups, appropriate methods should also spark creativity and enable the Urban Living Lab participants to innovate around their problem. In recent years, design-thinking has emerged as a set of creative problem-solving techniques used for the design of products and services. However, design-thinking can also be applied in urban planning. The [bootcamp bootleg](#) published by the Stanford d.school provides on its first pages an overview of the mindsets and stages of design-thinking.

Figure 2: Stanford d.school Design Thinking Process
(Source: <https://dschool.stanford.edu>)

Design-thinking guidelines are most often oblivious to power differentials and other restraints commonly encountered in urban planning that set real limits to a Living Lab’s creative leeway. Yet, creating an enabling, positive environment within the group and the workshops remains crucial and this is where design-thinking shines. To exemplify the spirit of design thinking workshops, we list some typical ideation principles:

- **All of you:** Bring all of your experiences, knowledge and expertise
- **Drop your agenda:** Listen to your co-designer and keep an open mind
- **Defer judgement:** You never know what will trigger a great idea. Don’t jump to edit, comment or worry about execution.
- **Encourage wild ideas:** Take creative leaps without constraints
- **Build on the ideas of others:** Use “yes, and...” instead of “no, but..”
- **Stay focused:** On the goal of...
- **One conversation at a time:** Listen attentively
- **Be visual:** Draw it, doodle it, colour it
- **Go for quantity:** As many ideas as possible
- **Don’t look back:** Don’t dismiss something just because it has been tried before

Implementing such principles within Living Labs may be very beneficial to group dynamics and creative output. We have therefore embedded the design-thinking stages – empathize, define, ideate, prototype, test – into the LOOPER co-creation process laid out in the next section.

5.4

5.5 What are the stages of co-creation as defined in LOOPER?

There are multiple ways to classify the various stages of co-creation. Within LOOPER, the co-creative planning process is conceptualized by the LOOPER platform, which comprises three sequential planning stages that form the basis of each living lab (Figure 3). This three-stage process will be conducted twice in each urban living lab to demonstrate their iterative character, as well as the ongoing processes of contextualisation, deliberation, decision-making, and implementation.

Figure 3: Conceptualization of the LOOPER process (initial proposal extended based on design methodology literature)

The main stages of the LOOPER methodology are as follows:

1. **Identification of problems and opportunities:** The aim is to identify the problems of a local community through a three-step process. This stage can be framed positively, referring to opportunities rather than problems:
 - 1a. **Scoping:** The affected communities and the context of the problems will be identified. The problems will be framed in a way to enable the tangible aspects to be identified through data.
 - **Co-Empathise: Understanding other participants**
 - **Explore Problems: Collecting and exploring problems (broadening)**
 - **Define Problem: Defining the problem to tackle (focusing)**
 - 1b. **Data collection:** Data to identify the scope, location and type of problems will be collected with the participation of stakeholders via participatory sensing, via public databases and through face-to-face discussions.
 - 1c. **Visualisation:** Visualisations of collected data will be published on the LOOPER platform for each living lab and discussed at local workshops.
2. **Co-design and evaluation of alternative solutions:** The aim of this stage is to assess the problems identified in the previous stage, co-design and evaluate solutions, and select the solution(s) that will be implemented.
 - 2a. **Co-design:** Participants will engage in qualitative and interactive online and face-to-face deliberation activities to propose solutions. Participants will co-create alternative scenarios, explore new synergies in design or policy and define pathways for action.
 - **Ideate: Collect and generate Ideas (thinking broadly)**
 - **Design: Refine and expand upon idea(s) (focused creative thinking)**
 - **Test: Prototype and finalize idea (focused practical thinking)**
 - 2b. **Evaluation:** Moments of evaluation can take place throughout the process, wherever the Living Lab has to converge on a next step forward. If after the co-design stage clear options to choose amongst

arise, a more standardized method like a multi-criteria analysis will be used to appraise the sustainability of alternatives and the Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) will be used to identify stakeholders' preferences.

- **Organize: Ranking, merging and selecting of ideas/problems/opportunities (synthesizing thoughts)**
- **Evaluate: Check for popularity, sustainability, feasibility etc. (reality check)**
- **Agree: Compromising and consensus building, group facilitation for mutually agreed outcomes**

3. **Implementation and monitoring:** Based on the results of Stage 2, stakeholders will implement a range of solutions and monitor their efficiency, using the same or comparable data used for the problem definition (Stage 1).
 - 3a. **Implementation** in the living labs will involve citizens and stakeholders through their voluntary contribution.
 - 3b. **Monitoring:** Monitoring the impact of co-designed solutions will use the same set of tools as in Stage 1. This may involve participants through participatory sensing and open data or through other qualitative means of appraisal like reconducting interviews.

The methods reviewed will be useful in facilitating progress in one or more steps during the preliminary scoping, co-design or evaluation aspects of the process. Each method has therefore been assessed in its usefulness to aide citizens to **empathize** with each other, **explore problems, define problems, ideate, design** or **test** ideas as well as **organize, evaluate** and **agree** on solutions. Where applicable, methods are also ranked in their strength to facilitate **data collection, data visualization, implementation** and **monitoring**. However, it was not the focus of the deliverable to review methods targeted towards these stages.

In addition, we would like to highlight that the co-design of ideas and the evaluation of ideas should happen in parallel rather than subsequently. After a phase of creative and unbounded ideation, one would look for intermediate reality checks, merging of ideas and compromise to eliminate what is not feasible. Instead, one would reiterate more on ideas which were already received positively and for which a broader consensus was already found. The Living Lab should collaborate and compromise along a single proposal, rather than developing multiple competing solutions.

6 METHODOLOGY

At the heart of these guidelines is the review of co-design tools, both online and face-to-face. The table with all reviewed tools can be found in the appendix. Among the 69 tools initially reviewed, a sub-selection of 21 diverse tools were studied in greater detail and a full factsheet was created. These tools are to be seen as potentially complimentary, many of them can be utilized in a Living Lab. In general, we avoided making factsheets of identical tools. An exception to this are the sheets on all-in-one online platforms. As these would be a high financial commitment, we chose to look at multiple in depth.

6.1 Review methodology

Methods for co-creation are available in many different forms, ranging from publications on government or NGO websites, to interactive websites, wikis, prepared toolkits for sale, publications of source code of pilot projects that have never been made available as software, to case study narratives of past projects. In terms of online platforms, some are non-profit but many are start-ups selling their services to public bodies in a specific region. Many of these have never been discussed in academic publications. While marketed to different audiences, their underlying concepts may be similar. To efficiently scope such a broad range of potential tools, it was not feasible to conduct a systematic review of academic literature. Instead, an informed convenience review was undertaken, parsing through online results produced by relevant key words. We also broadened the terminology to other professional domains

where similar methods are employed under different names. We therefore carried out an internet search using the following key words:

Table 1: Keywords used when conducting review (also used in combination with one term per column)

7 DEBRIEF OF TOOL FEATURES

There is a wide range of products which can be useful to co-design solutions. However, a key part of co-design is the open innovation format and specific circumstances may only emerge during the process. Often it is unclear what type of solution (redesign of public space, routing of traffic, new service, new ruling like new speed limit, limited access rights during weekends) will emerge. In fact, predefined problem framings and solutions are to be avoided as they limit innovation (Scholl et al., 2017). Yet, predefined problem framings might help participants to work more constructively as they can avoid off topic discussions.. Similarly, having an already predefined set of tools might limit innovation, yet streamline the process. In Living Labs like LOOPER, it is therefore difficult to predict what will be the most appropriate tool and instead, one needs to leave some room to react flexibly to evolving circumstances.

This review therefore remains broad and is a scoping of which tools exist. The Living Labs will be able to choose the most appropriate tool based on their specific needs. These tools and their intended application will be mentioned in the Living Lab implementation plans (D5.1; D6.1; D7.1). A template for the Living Lab implementation plans is included in D4.1.

We now introduce the structure of our factsheets followed by a debrief on the classifications used. During the review, the following features of the tools have been identified and are listed on the fact sheets:

- **The name, the organisation** behind a tool and the **country of origin**
- **Language:** The language of the tool and the possibility of translating the tool into another language.
- **Proprietary status:** as far as possible, we noted whether a product was published under a Creative Commons license and whether the product was (not) for profit
- **Developmental status:** non-accessible inspiration, source code, plug-in, full software, full subscription service
- **Price estimate:** Where applicable the **price** is listed.

In a next step, we found that there are two general approaches to grouping the reviewed tools: The first one is by the intended “audience”, i.e. based on the underpinning theoretical roots, targeted solutions, and professional discipline in which a given tool evolved. The second way to group tools is by “medium” (online, face-to-face) and specific “category” (handbook, game, training). Once embedded in the LOOPER platform, one will easily filter these according to preference.

- **Audience:** the methods of co-design are applied in various contexts. While similarly trying to engage all stakeholders and creatively innovate, the type of solution designed (physical object or a service?) or the underlying theoretical roots may differ. The audiences are further detailed in section 7.1.
- **Medium:** Is the tool **digital** (software or hardware which requires a computer but not necessarily web access) **online** (focused on online interaction) or meant to be used **face-to-face** (interaction in workshops)?
- **Category:** Various types of tools exist which can enhance the quality of a Living Lab. **Toolkits** provide a ready-to-use set of (sometimes physical) materials for workshops. **Facilitation handbooks** are brochures or books that provide a range of workshop methods to choose from, of which some are online repositories of methods. The category **Discourse** includes tools (mostly online) enabling communication between citizens. **Games** allow for a playful approach to the problem. **Trainings** are offered online and offline to improve a facilitator’s workshop skills.

In section 5.4, we defined the three co-creation stages and fourteen co-creation steps in LOOPER (see Figure 3). We found it relevant to assess each tool in its coverage of these stages. For handbooks containing multiple methods, we checked for which stages a method is available.

- **Co-Design stages covered:** On the right upper side of the factsheet, those stages covered by the tools are written in black while not (sufficiently) covered stages are written in white.

Lastly, in light of the LOOPER project, we made a subjective estimation on a scale from 1 to 5 (with 5 being the easiest) regarding the ease of which any given tool could be implemented in the ongoing project. As this rating is highly specific to the LOOPER circumstances and the factsheets already represent a sub-selection of the potentially most appropriate tools, this rating may be deleted.

- **Ease of implementation:** An estimate is made regarding the **degree of difficulty** of implementing a tool within the LOOPER living labs and the online platform (with 5 out of 5 being the easiest).
- **Requirements for implementation:** Where applicable, the needed resources are listed. These may be online-access during workshops, server for hosting, programming skills, NGO/Academic status for free access, etc.

7.1 Audiences – Co-Design in its various contexts

In the following section, we identify four areas in which co-design and participatory approaches are employed in professional practice. During the review, we found four professional fields or audiences emerging as recurring themes in the way tools are targeted and framed. We propose the below grouping as guidance and claim that most surveyed tools can be classified in one of these streams. The different streams differ in the theoretical roots and academic fields from which they emerged and determine for which audience and context a tool has been developed. The kind of solution developed (a service, an object, a public space) also tends to differ.

7.1.1 Public Service Design

One co-design audience is the public sector for (re)designing services. Numerous toolboxes have been created by public institutions (often national bodies) who collated useful tools and handbooks for their local agencies to redesign services with their users. These are at their core focused on improving the experience of users of the service. An example would be: how can we improve the experience of delivering warm lunches to the elderly, both for the receiving person, their caretakers and the employee delivering the meals? Designing a service lends itself to different methods than designing a physical

object. Ideation sessions often revolve around roleplay or the “travel” of a person through the bureaucracy when accessing a service.

“Service Co-Design” tools are mostly aimed at public officials or NGOs working on improving a service together with the receivers of that service. These tools often aim to improve an experience (e.g. the service of receiving dialysis for chronically ill patients; the process of submitting a complaint to the local government).

7.1.2 Collaborative Planning

In the Urban and Spatial Planning sector, “Collaborative Planning” has become a popular term (Patsy Healey, 1997; Innes and Booher, 2010). Depending on the country, and whether in an academic or professional context, it is now often a common position that urban planning professionals understand themselves as facilitators rather than experts. They bring the necessary tools and some technical knowledge to the table to enable collaborative decision with stakeholders. Especially where urban planning conflicts have reached a gridlock, planning professionals furthermore turn to consensus-building approaches which propose that continued value-based conversation between disagreeing parties can lead to mutually beneficial outcomes (Innes and Booher, 2010).

“Collaborative Planning” handbooks are targeted towards urban planning professionals and are more likely to revolve around physical interventions, managing the conflicting interests around the use of public space, and may consider longer planning horizons.

7.1.3 Design Thinking

Design Thinking (Brown and Wyatt, 2010) describes an academic and popular science field that takes the designer’s approach to innovation to solve real-world conflicts. Here, the focus is much more on the methodology of how a problem is thought about, rather than the interaction between laypeople and designers. It stipulates that the way designers think about problems is effective and even people working outside of the traditional design fields should learn to think like designers when tackling problems. Therefore, many methods propagated by design thinking will likely be highly effective in sparking creativity in urban contexts.

“Design Thinking” tools are very broad and can be targeted towards a product or a social innovation. They are likely to aim for something disruptive and foster “thinking out of the box” more than other handbooks.

7.1.4 Public Participation

Public participation tools are part of a broader development towards increasing the engagement of citizens in decision-making processes in public administrations. Aside from some facilitation handbooks, most tools surveyed in this category were online websites. Termed as e-democracy, all-in-one websites are offered to municipalities for their public engagement processes. The rationale behind putting public engagement online is that it allows for transparency and continuous flow of information. However, stakeholder engagement cannot be taken care of simply by launching a website. Most often, there is not enough participatory culture for real online democracy to take place without parallel face-to-face sessions. Instead, only a minority of the population participates and real-world work (interacting face-to-face) gets neglected. In addition, going beyond simple information gathering towards empathizing, developing shared values, compromising and consensus-building is hard to achieve without face to face dialogue. For real civil discourse, these online tools would let users explore the variety of opinions and allow for people to change their opinion rather than just give it. However, some parts of the public may indeed only be reached through online channels, and its transparency and openness are valuable.

“Public Participation” tools aim to broaden the base of participants, enabling interaction in the online realm that usually takes place face-to-face.

We provide factsheets on the “Urb@exp Lab Kit” and the “KETSU Toolkit”.

7.2.2 Facilitation handbooks

Some of the handbooks are broad in their scope and are a collection of workshop ideas. For more experienced facilitators, it can be handy to have a broader range of methods at hand to be more flexible and respond to needs. These handbooks include a short guidance for the facilitator(s) of a living lab as well as a toolbox with single methods - workshop activities – that can be carried out face-to-face with a group. It is up to the facilitator to choose from the options as he/she sees fit. Here there are many competing/overlapping products and most of them freely available as PDF-file. Beside co-design, many of these handbooks also go to earlier and later stages, detailing how to reach out and engage individuals, and how to follow up on outcomes.

The handbooks will have a different “tone” depending on the intended audience. Relevant factsheets are provided for “COPack - Collaborative planning methods manual”, “Participatory Methods Toolkit”, “Participedia”, “Hyper Island Toolbox”, “Service Design Tools”, and the “Collective Action Toolkit”.

7.2.3 Online training courses for facilitation

Workshops stand and fall with good facilitation, so the person leading workshops may profit from online training courses. Some of the handbooks presented earlier provide very detailed introductory chapters on good workshop facilitation.

Aspects for which facilitator can seek training:

- Good preparation (pre-meeting checklists)
- Basics in shaping a space for constructive discussion
- Basics in supporting a group in developing cooperative and respectful work atmosphere
- Discussion facilitation methods leading to the group’s work becoming more streamlined and more rewarding for participants
- Mediation and conflict resolution skills

For the design aspect, online webinars and courses can be found on massive open online courses (MOOCs) websites under the keyword “design thinking” ([Coursera: Design Thinking Innovation](#); [COursera: design-thinking-greater-good-innovation-social-sector](#); [Coursera: Innovation Publique](#))

The Stanford d.school offers a free [virtual crash course](#). Rather than passively watching a course, it gives instruction on how to run a 90-minute ideation session, that the learner can undertake with 2+ participants.

IDEO is a consulting firm which has launched an online webinar service [IDEO U](#) in 2017 and their 5-week course costs 399 dollars.

Hyper Island, also a consultancy and business school, offers a "[Workshop Planning Kit](#)" containing 60 cards with all factors to be considered when setting up the workshop format (free to print, 49€ to order;). These can be helpful for a Living lab facilitator. Training courses are offered in London, Stockholm and Singapore (at a cost).

For face-to-face trainings, the most renowned yet affordable design thinking school in Europe is the [School of Design Thinking](#) of the Hasso Plattner Institute in Potsdam, Germany.

Relevant factsheets are on the “CoPack’s Collaborative Planning Trainer’s Guide”.

7.2.4 Single Methods

Single workshop methods (i.e. a 2-hour workshop session) are not described within this review. Many of the handbooks do a great job in comparing these side by side and providing step-by-step manuals. As the Living Labs progress, such method choices will be detailed in the Living Lab Implementation plans.

7.3 Online Tools

Online products and services can be very useful in co-creation processes as they allow participants to participate at a time and location to their choosing. Online participation may also lead to more diverse results, as all participants have equal opportunities to voice their opinions. Nevertheless, online co-creation processes exclude citizens who do not own a computer or mobile device.

The products and services reviewed in this section range from simple commenting plug-ins for websites to complete ready-to-use platforms that enable all steps of the co-creation process. While more simple applications with one specific function often are often cheap or free of charge, all-in-one software packages created for local governments can be costly. Moreover, whereas simple plugins can be incorporated in the LOOPER platform, this may prove more difficult with complete software packages. And even though these applications may prove useful for some local governments, their functions are often not revolutionary nor copyright protected and can therefore be duplicated.

It should be noted that although the selected tools give a good overview what is possible in terms of online co-creation, this is by no means an exhaustive list. When setting up a co-creation platform, always select tools that fulfil the set requirements and that participants and practitioners are comfortable using.

7.3.1 Multi-purpose online tools

Many online products and services have several functions that can be useful in multiple co-design steps. These functions range from posting comments to drawing mind maps. For example, a commenting plug-in can be used to empathise with other users as well as to ideate and evaluate solutions.

Online plug-ins are snippets of source code or web applications that can be integrated into the LOOPER platform. Two similar commenting plug-ins are [Disqus](#) and [Isso](#), of which the latter is open-source. These plug-ins allow users to comment on articles as well as to debate with each other. Since their functionality usually is limited, small co-design platforms can use the free versions. Especially open-source applications require technical knowledge before they can be integrated into a co-design platform.

There are many online applications and platforms that serve several steps of the co-design process. Whereas some can be integrated into the LOOPER platform, others are stand-alone applications. Most services have functionalities that allow users to identify problems and co-design and evaluate solutions. Some services go one step further, and provide opportunity for users to implement and monitor solutions. All services have a free option that has limited functionalities, but will require a premium subscription if used for co-design purposes.

Relevant factsheets are on “Loomio”, “Slack”, “Trello”, “Stormboard”, “Idea Flip”, “Streetmix”, “Smart Citizen”, and “MindMeister”.

7.3.2 All-in-one

Several online platforms enable local governments to follow all steps of the co-creation process. Although these platforms provide an all-in-one solution, this is compensated by a high price tag.

Factsheets in this category are on “TransformCity”, “Fluicity”, “CitizenLab” and “ParticipatiePlatform”.

7.4 Digital Tools

As the Living labs will progress and it becomes apparent what type of solution will be designed, specialized software may become useful. This depends heavily on the digital affinity of the Living Lab participants. The added value that a digital and accurate model may bring over a creation made from cardboard needs to be critically evaluated. Being limited by their capacity to manipulate a model using such software can hamper the creativity of citizens. A compromise could be to create physical models from simple materials within the group and then let other participants convert it into a digital version.

7.4.1 Virtual reality

For the exploration of the current state of a space, one could employ 360-degree camera shots to enable 3D commenting. In order to get an impression of a proposal before its physical implementation, virtual reality models are also an option. The necessary resources may however not be proportional to the achieved added benefits: Filming or modelling may be very time intensive while usage through people could just as much as when simpler methods (2D photographs) were used.

7.4.2 Computer games

[Cities: Skylines](#) is a city simulator that may provide enough modding functions (the possibility to add custom functions or change game mechanics as necessary) and a complex enough traffic simulation that it could be used within Living Labs focusing on traffic flow. If a few participants are eager to rebuild their neighbourhood or the proposed solution in the game, it allows to simulate traffic flux throughout the day and players can choose to take on the perspective of one of the virtual inhabitants.

7.4.3 3D modelling

Urban Planners and Architects use 3D modelling tools to build models. The learning curve of these tools is steep and Living Lab participants may not be able to use them independently. Examples are the ESRI city engine [ESRI City Engine](#) or [SketchUp](#). SketchUp may be challenging for a layperson to get used to. When redesigning a street or square, it would allow to import a 2D plan of the area upon which to design.

Figure 5: Sample model in SketchUp

(Source: http://www.architectmagazine.com/technology/modeling-skills-final-day-at-sketchup-3d-basecamp-2014_o)

8 FACTSHEETS

LAB kit

An Urban Lab in a Day: Laying the Groundwork

Face-to-Face
Toolkit

By: urb@exp

Audience: Collaborative Planning

Languages: EN

Country of Origin: Netherlands and others

Proprietary Status: Creative Commons

Price: 100 €

Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5

Requirements:

Use when...

setting up a Living Lab framework by considering potential problems right from the start

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

The LAB kit has been designed as a tool for inspiration to help municipalities or other stakeholders in a city on their way in drafting or sharpening the outlines of an urban lab. The LAB kit helps to raise and discuss key questions that are worth asking before engaging in such an endeavour. It is the outcome of a collaborative effort between researchers and practitioners and has been tested with various potential user groups.

Links:

<http://www.urbanexp.eu/>

http://www.urbanexp.eu/data/GUIDELINES_270617.pdf

Similar Resources:

KETSO

Face-to-Face Toolkit

The hands-on kit for creative engagement

By: Ketso Ltd.

Audience: Collaborative Planning

Languages: universal

Country of Origin: UK

Proprietary Status: Product for Purchase

Price: 300€ -600€

Ease of Implementation: 3 out of 5

Requirements:

Use when...

budget is available for durable and re-usable workshop materials

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Ketso is a hands-on kit for creative engagement, useful in encouraging ideas and thoughts from all participants. Ketso can be used in workshops with a facilitator to form a structured way of encouraging participation and to prompt discussions. Ideas are written down on re-usable material and the information is captured in a compact structure. It is a re-usable set of tabletop tools to capture and display people's ideas. It is not aimed at a specific niche and can be used in all sorts of team discussions. Main components are a user guide provided in English, a workspace made from felt, and dryerase cards that can be stuck to the felt surface. From a sustainability point of view it would be preferable to have such reusable materials.

Links:

<http://www.ketso.com/>

Similar Resources:

COPack

Collaborative Planning Methods Manual

By: Oulu University of Applied Sciences
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN
Country of Origin: Finland and others
Proprietary Status: Creative Commons
Price: free
Ease of Implementation: 3 out of 5
Requirements:

Use when...

looking for a systematic and in-depth review of collaborative planning methods

- Empathize
- Explore
- Define
- Collect Data
- Visualize
- Ideate
- Design
- Test
- Organize
- Evaluate
- Agree
- Implement
- Monitor

COPack is an EU-funded project from 2012 that produced a Methods Manual with an in-depth survey of 25 workshop methods and rates them on various scales: Understandability, Quantification, Expertise needed, Equipment needed. It also assesses the degree to which they suit different project stages: Problem Identification, Problem Structuring, Problem Solving. Each method is described, its benefits and drawbacks are highlighted and further resources are listed. This toolkit is quite academic and more suited for researchers or professionals that want to receive in-depth reviews rather than a ready-to-use product. However, the information provided is very rich and targeted more towards Urban Planners than many other toolkits.

Table 1: Applicability of methods to different stages of a collaborative process

	Problem identification	Problem structuring	Problem solving
3-6-5 Brainwriting	○		●
Action Learning	○	●	●
AHP		●	○
ANP		●	○
A'WOT	●	○	○
Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN)	○	●	○
CatPac	●		
CATWOE	○	●	
Cognitive Mapping	●	○	○
Design Charrette	●	○	○

Links:

<http://copack.oamk.fi/>
http://copack.oamk.fi/docs/methods/methods_manual.pdf
http://www.oamk.fi/hankkeet/tracopi/media/tables_wp2.pdf

Similar Resources:

Participatory

Methods Toolkit - A practitioners manual (New edition)

By: King Bauduin Foundation and Flemish Institute for Technology

Audience: Public Participation

Languages: EN NL

Country of Origin: Belgium

Proprietary Status: Creative Commons

Price: free

Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5

Requirements:

Use when...

looking for a full guide on a participatory process

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Participatory is a hands-on toolkit for starting and managing participatory project developed by the King Baudouin Foundation and the Flemish Institute for Science and Technology Assessment (viWTA). The toolkit focusses on any type of decision-making process to the public. The toolkit comprises 13 in-depth fiches on the most promising participatory methods. A chapter with general guidelines for using participatory methods includes a comparative chart of the discussed methods as well as an overview of 50 methods and techniques. The descriptions of the 13 methods are in-depth and oriented towards practicalities (at least 10 pages for each, with suggested timelines, prep lists, workshop plans). While these methods might be described in other toolkits, it can be useful to check in this publication for the most detailed step-by-step practicalities.

Links:

<https://www.kbs-frb.be/en/Virtual-Library/2006/294864>:

Similar Resources:

<p>15 weeks from event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decide on the meeting date and size Secure meeting site Complete preliminary budget Form an Executive Team Identify stakeholders Identify funding sources and co-sponsors 	<p>10 weeks from event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop plans for website Develop plans for registration Finalize key media strategies Complete first program design Finalize staging, AV, event management Draft outreach materials Begin recruiting theme team and issue experts
<p>14 weeks from event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preliminary discussion on content/design Continue to identify stakeholders Identify contractors to serve as local staff Develop "Behind the Scenes" event for invited guests interested in the process 	<p>9 weeks from event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalize work area strategies and work plans Finalize outreach materials Launch facilitator recruitment; set training dates Launch outreach Review 1st draft of Participant Guide Launch Outreach
<p>13 weeks from event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Determine outreach goals Finalize staffing assignments Determine requirements for content Develop plan and schedule for Executive Team Prepare matrix of data sources for content 	<p>8 weeks from event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launch website Launch registration (online & phone) Launch outreach Finalize plan for special services (e.g., childcare) Interview remaining consultants/vendors

COMPARATIVE CHART FOR PARTICIPATORY METHODS

Method	Objectives	Topic*				Participants	Time		€
		Knowledge	Maturity	Complexity	Controversial		Event	Total	
21 st Century Town Meeting	to engage thousands of people at a time (up to 5000 per meeting) in deliberation about complex public policy issues	+	+/-	+	+/-	Anyone	1-3 days	a year	4
Charrette	Generate consensus among diverse groups of people and form an action plan.	+/-	+/-	-	+/-	Average citizens or stakeholders. Others give input.	1-5 days	2-3 months	3
Citizens Jury	A decision that is representative of average citizens who have been well informed on the issue. Aims	+/-	+/-	+/-	+	12-24 randomly selected citizens. Experts, stakeholders & politicians give input.	3 days	4-5 months	4
Consensus Conference	Consensus and a decision on a controversial topic.	+	+/-	+	+	10-30 randomly selected citizens. Others give input.	3 weekends	7-12 months	4
Deliberative polling ⁹	to get both a representative and an informed (deliberative) view of what the public thinks and feels about an important public issue	-	+/-	-	+/-	A random and representative sample of the population	1 day	8 months	4
Delphi	Expose all opinions & options regarding a complex issue.	-	-	+	+/-	Experts	Variable	Variable	1-3
Expert Panel	Synthesize a variety of inputs on a specialised topic and produce recommendations.	-	-	+	+/-	Experts	Variable	Variable	2
Focus Group	Expose different groups' opinions on an issue and why these are held (reasoning).	+/-	-	m	+/-	Stakeholders and/or citizens	2 hours - 1 day	1 month	1
PAME	Evaluating and learning	+/-	+/-	+/-	+/-	All stakeholders	Variable	Variable	Var

Participedia

Strengthen democracy through shared methods

Face-to-Face Handbook

By: The University of British Columbia
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN DE
Country of Origin: Canada
Proprietary Status: Creative Commons
Price: free
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements:

Use when...

looking for case studies or when wanting a filtered set of methods for specific circumstances

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Participedia is a well managed wiki of participatory methods across all fields. Anyone can join the Participedia community and help crowdsource, catalogue and compare participatory political processes around the world. All content on Participedia is collaboratively produced and open-source under a Creative Commons License. Both a searchable database of case studies and of methods are offered. The quality of the methods descriptions vary enormously with some being excellent (34 are complete) while others are mere stubs (82). Yet with 233 entries, one is likely to find something relevant or additional information on an approach already discovered elsewhere.

Links:

<https://participedia.net/en>

Similar Resources:

Participatory Methods (<http://www.participatorymethods.org>)

Hyper Island

Toolbox

Face-to-Face Handbook

By: Hyper Island

Audience: Design Thinking

Languages: EN

Country of Origin: Singapore

Proprietary Status: Copyrighted by for-profit company

Price: free

Ease of Implementation: 4 out of 5

Requirements:

Use when...

looking for energizing and group-building activities or methods geared towards setting up a project

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Consultancy and business school Hyper Island offers an online repository of methods for general creative collaboration in any team or organization. This includes, much more than other handbooks presented, also Energizers, Team Building and Self-Leadership activities. The 75 activities can be sorted by time frame and by group size. Hyper Island also offers a "Workshop Planning Kit" that contains 60 cards with all factors to be considered when setting up the workshop format (free to print, 49€ to order). These can be helpful for a Living lab facilitator. Training courses are offered in London, Stockholm and Singapore (at a cost).

Links:

<http://toolbox.hyperisland.com/>

<https://www.hyperisland.com/community/news/a-free-kit-for-planning-workshops>

Similar Resources:

Service Design Tools

Face-to-Face
Handbook

By: Roberta Tassi (Politecnico di Milano)
Audience: Service Design
Languages: EN
Country of Origin: Italy
Proprietary Status: Creative Commons
Price: free
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements:

Use when...

designing a service,
looking for case study
examples, or wanting
an overview of the ori-
gin of tools.

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Service Design Tools is a website with short descriptions for 36 tools useful in communication design and service design. It was compiled by a PhD student as part of her graduate research at Milan Technical University. The tools can be filtered by design stage, type of representations created, and by recipient. A short glossary of terms is also provided as well as an overview of the disciplines and time the listed tools originated. Tools are described and illustrated with a case study. However, step-by-step guides for the tools are missing. A similar resource by Pilotlight provides such guides for 18 tools.

SERVICE DESIGN TOOLS
COMMUNICATION METHODS SUPPORTING DESIGN PROCESSES

DESIGN ACTIVITIES	REPRESENTATIONS	RECIPIENTS	CONTENTS
CO-DESIGNING	TEXTS	STAKEHOLDERS	CONTEXT
ENVISIONING	GRAPHS	PROFESSIONALS	SYSTEM
TESTING & PROTOTYPING	NARRATIVES	SERVICE STAFF	OFFERING
IMPLEMENTING	GAMES	USERS	INTERACTION
	MODELS		

tool ROLE PLAY

tool description
Some actors, the sample users or the designers themselves perform a hypothetical service experience. The implied condition is thinking that the service really exists and then building a potential journey through some of its functionalities.

related
EXPERIENCE PROTOTYPE
DESIGN GAMES
LEGO SERIOUS PLAY™

A possible evolution of this tool consists in the performance of the same scene several times, changing the character profiles on each scene in order to understand how different users would act in the same situation.

Links:

<http://www.servicedesigntools.org/taxonomy/term/1>

Similar Resources:

Pilotlight (<http://pilotlight.iriss.org.uk/co-design/tools>)

Collective Action

Toolkit

Face-to-Face Handbook

By: Frog Design

Audience: Collaborative Planning

Languages: EN FR ES CH (further in progress)

Country of Origin: USA

Proprietary Status: Creative Commons

Price: free

Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5

Requirements:

Use when...

in need of immediate hands-on instructions for the next workshop

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

The Design Consultancy Frog has published an open-source Collective Action Toolkit encompassing straightforward method instructions for use by local change agents. Developed for developing countries, this booklet discusses 23 possible methods of about two hours each and proposes possible sequences in which to use them. The process towards achieving a goal is divided into six areas. Lastly, the booklet includes "learning cards" for participants to note personal experiences on what they learned. In its conciseness, the Toolkit does a great job in providing quick suggestions.

Links:

https://www.frogdesign.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/CAT_2.0_English.pdf

Similar Resources:

d.school bootcamp bootleg

PATTERN QUEST

Look closely at what group members discovered in their interviews to identify the deeper reasons why people struggle with certain issues.

TIME

1 hr.

ROLES

Participants
1 facilitator
1 timekeeper

MATERIALS

Printer paper, large paper, pens, a watch
Optional: camera, markers

WHERE TO NEXT?

Try an Imagine More Ideas activity area like 'Jam Session' to act on a topic that emerges from this activity.

- 1. Review**
Ask each person to share their interview notes and speak to the group.
- 2. Discuss**
Discuss the topics that people interviewed about. Listen at the end of each topic.
- 3. Divide**
Assign each team a topic to draw notes from the stories.
- 4. Review**
Finish by sharing the information.

COPack

Trainer's Guide

Face-to-Face Training

By: Oulu University of Applied Sciences

Audience: Collaborative Planning

Languages: EN NL DE FI HU SI CZ

Country of Origin: Finland and others

Proprietary Status: Creative Commons

Price: free

Ease of Implementation: 2 out of 5

Requirements:

Use when...

there is the opportunity to train co-creation facilitators in an educational setting

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

COPack is an EU-funded project from 2012 that produced a Trainer's Guide for Collaborative Planning. It has been designed to be used in vocational training and at universities, for the education of students and professionals involved in natural resources and environmental management planning. COPack consists of a set of materials such as handouts, exercises and slide shows to be used in lectures and courses. (A separate Methods Manual comprises the descriptions of more than 20 methods and tools for collaborative planning and instructions on how to use them.)

english | čeština | deutsch | magyar | nederlands | slovenčina | suomi

ides

2.1 Roles and attitudes

This lesson, in its first part, deals with different roles planners can and must assume in a collaborative group, as opposed to merely acting on a technical level of planning. The second part is dedicated to ethical considerations of decision-making. The two corresponding handouts can be presented during a 45-minute lesson or extended to cover 90 minutes so as to allow for discussion and in-depth learning. A basic, extensible slide show is also provided.

Handout 2.1.1 deals with the roles of planners in collaborative processes.

Handout 2.1.2 introduces three different approaches to decision-making.

The **Slides 2.1** presentation contains some text and images related to these topics.

The above topics are each accompanied by an exercise:

Exercise 2.1.1 aims at practising different roles in a given planning situation and requires preparation at home. Presentation and discussion of the results will take 20–60 min, depending on the number of students or groups.

In **Exercise 2.1.2**, students are requested to discuss a planning issue under different ethical approaches. Contrary to the preceding exercise, preparations will take place during the course, resulting in a time frame from 45 min upwards, depending on the number of groups.

EXERCISES

- [Exercise 2.1.1](#)
- [Exercise 2.1.2](#)

HANDOUTS

- [Handout 2.1.1](#)
- [Handout 2.1.2](#)

SLIDES

- [Slides 2.1](#)

Links:

http://copack.oamk.fi/docs/downloads/copack_trainers_guide.pdf

Similar Resources:

Loomio

Online
Discourse

By: Loomio

Audience: Collaborative Planning

Languages: EN FR

Country of Origin: New Zealand

Proprietary Status: Open Source

Price: \$0-\$99/month

Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5

Requirements: Internet connection; email address/social media account

Use when...

your project requires an online platform for discussion, co-design and decision-making

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Loomio is an online tool to make decisions in groups that allows commenting, voting and scheduling. The web platform can be used on desktop and mobile devices. Users can use existing social media accounts or use their email address in order to participate.

Links:

<https://www.loomio.org/>

Similar Resources:

Loomio, Trello

Slack

Online
Discourse

By: Slack
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN FR
Country of Origin: United States of America
Proprietary Status: Commercial
Price: €0-€11.75/user/month
Ease of Implementation: 4 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection; email address

Use when...

your projects requires an online messaging platform for brainstorming, co-design and co-decision

- Empathize
- Explore
- Define
- Collect Data
- Visualize
- Ideate
- Design
- Test
- Organize
- Evaluate
- Agree
- Implement
- Monitor

Slack is a software platform that provides a digital workspace where conversations are organized and accessible. Participants can communicate and discuss in groups, and vote in polls. Slack is available as desktop and mobile application. Account creation is required for access to platform. Small groups can use the free version.

Links:
<https://www.slack.com/>

Similar Resources:
Trello

Trello

Online
Discourse

By: Atlassian

Audience: Collaborative Planning

Languages: EN FR NL

Country of Origin: United States of America

Proprietary Status: Commercial

Price: \$0-\$20.83/month/user

Ease of Implementation: 4 out of 5

Requirements: Internet connection; email address/social media account

Use when...

your project needs an online platform to discuss problems, their solutions, and the impact of solution

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Trello is an online platform that allows users to collaborate on boards, lists, and cards. Users can create groups and develop and comment on ideas. It is available as a webpage and as a mobile application. Users can use existing social media accounts or set up an account with Trello in order to participate in the platform.

Links:

<https://trello.com>

Similar Resources:

Loomio

Stormboard

Online
Discourse

By: StormBoard

Audience: Collaborative Planning

Languages: EN (can be adjusted)

Country of Origin: Canada

Proprietary Status: Commercial

Price: \$0-\$8.33/month/user

Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5

Requirements: Internet connection; email address/social media account

Use when...

your project needs a comprehensive ready-to-use project management tool for idea creation, co-design and co-decision, and review

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Stormboard allows users to define objectives, brainstorm and organize ideas, and plan and review projects. Users can animate ideas in various ways, such as sticky notes, images, and sketches. Users can use existing social media accounts or set up a Stormboard account in order to access the platform. Stormboard can be used on desktops as well as mobile devices.

Links:

<https://www.stormboard.com/>

Similar Resources:

IdeaFlip

Online
Discourse

By: BiggerFlip
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN
Country of Origin: United Kingdom
Proprietary Status: Commercial
Price: \$9-\$16/month
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection; email address/social media account

Use when...

your project requires a visual online platform where ideas can be exchanged, merged and agreed on

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

IdeaFlip is an online tool for collecting, developing and discussing ideas, problems and solutions. It is an online whiteboard on which participants can share and develop ideas on sticky notes. The platform is accesible on desktop and mobile devices. Account creation is possible but not necessary in order to participate in the platform.

Links:

<https://ideafli.com/>

Similar Resources:

Streetmix

Online
Site Modelling

By: Streetmix
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN
Country of Origin: United States of America
Proprietary Status: Open Source
Price: Free
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection

Use when...

redesigning a street is
part of your project

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Streetmix is a web application that allows users to (re)design a street by allocating space to different types of road use. Users can add elements such as bike lanes, bus lanes, transit stops and sidewalks. Streetmix is an easy-to-use and visual co-design tool. The tool only works on tablets and computers.

Links:

<https://www.streetmix.net>

Similar Resources:

Smart Citizen

Online; Digital
Data Collection

By: Smart Citizen
Audience: Public Participation
Languages: EN
Country of Origin: Spain
Proprietary Status: Open Source
Price: Free
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection

Use when...

environmental data collection is part of your project

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Smart Citizen is a platform that allows citizens to collect and share environmental data such as air quality and noise pollution. Users can access the online platform where they see real-time information from different data collection points. Users can also purchase a kit which allows them to collect data and contribute to the platform. The website can be used on mobile devices as well as computers, and there is also an Android app. Account creation is not required for access to the platform.

Links:

<https://smartcitizen.me/>

Similar Resources:

MindMeister

Online
Discourse

By: MeisterLabs
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN FR NL
Country of Origin: Austria
Proprietary Status: Commercial
Price: \$0-\$12.49/month/user
Ease of Implementation: 4 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection; email address/social media account

Use when...

your project needs an online mind mapping tool that allows users to develop, share and agree on ideas visually

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

MindMeister is an online mindmapping tool that allows users to collaborate online and capture, develop and share ideas visually. It can be used for brainstorming, note taking and project planning. The web application works on desktops and mobile devices. Users can gain access to the platform with their social media account or by setting up a MindMeister account, but it is not necessary to have an account when editing an existing board.

Links:

<https://www.mindmeister.com/>

Similar Resources:

TransformCity

Online
Discourse

By: TransformCity
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN NL
Country of Origin: Netherlands
Proprietary Status: Commercial
Price: On request
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection

Use when...

your project needs a comprehensive ready-to-use co-design tool and has sufficient financial resources

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

TransformCity allows citizens to participate in the collective shaping of an urban vision and understand and appreciate the transformation process via a timeline. Citizens, city planners and stakeholders can introduce new ideas and projects, make direct comments and test and gain local support. Users can point out locations on a map and note their ideas. The first TransformCity pilot was in Amsterdam in 2016, and the municipality has chosen to implement the platform in two of its largest transformation districts. Account creation is required for participation.

Links:

<http://www.transformcity.com/>

<https://vimeo.com/166327782>

<http://www.zocity.nl/interactieve-kaart>

Similar Resources:

Fluicity, CitizenLab, Participatie Platform

Fluicity

Online
Discourse

By: Fluicity
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN FR NL
Country of Origin: France
Proprietary Status: Commercial
Price: On request
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection; email address/social media account

Use when...

your project needs a ready-to-use co-design tool that focuses on dialogue between stakeholders and has available financial resources

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

Fluicity is a platform that enables dialogue between elected officials and citizens. Citizens can suggest ideas for their municipality, speak to elected officials and take part in polls through a mobile application and a website. The platform also shows news updates and allows for messaging between citizens and local stakeholders. Fluicity is used in several cities in Belgium and France.

Links:

<https://www.flui.city/>

Similar Resources:

TransformCity, CitizenLab, Participatie Platform

CitizenLab

Online
Discourse

By: CitizenLab
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN FR NL
Country of Origin: Belgium
Proprietary Status: Private
Price: On request
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection; email address/social media account

Use when...

your project needs a comprehensive ready-to-use co-design tool and has sufficient financial resources

Empathize

Explore

Define

Collect Data

Visualize

Ideate

Design

Test

Organize

Evaluate

Agree

Implement

Monitor

CitizenLab is an online co-creation tool that allows citizens to directly engage with each other as well as with local governments. Citizens can submit proposals, collaborate on ideas and vote on suggestions via an online platform. Users can point out locations on a map and note their ideas. Local governments get a better understanding of the citizens' needs. Citizens can use existing social media accounts or create a new account on the platform in order to participate.

Links:

<https://www.citizenlab.co/>
<https://demo.citizenlab.co/>

Similar Resources:

TransformCity, Fluitcity, Participatie Platform

ParticipatiePlatform

Online
Discourse

By: Treecompany
Audience: Collaborative Planning
Languages: EN FR NL
Country of Origin: Belgium
Proprietary Status: Commercial
Price: On request
Ease of Implementation: 5 out of 5
Requirements: Internet connection

Use when...

your project requires input from stakeholders, but the final say rests with decision makers

Empathize
Explore
Define
Collect Data
Visualize
Ideate
Design
Test
Organize
Evaluate
Agree
Implement
Monitor

ParticipatiePlatform is a web-based platform that allows groups of people to discuss, develop and vote on ideas. The goal, method and research question are defined by the organiser before citizens participate. Several municipalities in Belgium have used the platform to engage citizens in solving urban problems as well as developing policies.

Links:

<http://participatieplatform.treecompany.be/>

Similar Resources:

TransformCity, Flucicity, CitizenLab

9 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has created a catalogue of resources potentially applicable in the LOOPER Living Lab process. As the Living Labs become more concrete, resources can be chosen according to the evolving needs. While this review has deliberately remained broad to account for needed flexibility, we would nonetheless provide a general first direction:

For face-to-face interaction, a wealth of handbooks has been found. A good start are the introductory chapters of the [Participatory Methods Toolkit](#) by the King Baudouin Foundation, followed by a look-over of the 23 methods in the [Collective Action Toolkit](#) by Frog Design or the [bootcamp bootleg](#) of Stanford's d-school. The urb@exp [LAB kit](#) can be employed at the inception of the Living Lab or if direction and structure is lacking during its implementation. When reaching the creative stage, Stanford's [virtual crash course](#) can be a great engaging 90-minute activity for participants to provide them with creative energy and methods to tackle their problems.

Online co-creation tools have a great variety of functionalities that can be incorporated into online co-creation platforms. As communication is of vital importance in the co-creation process, a co-creation platform should always include a messaging and commenting functionality. Which other tools are most useful depends on the needs of a platform, the technical knowledge of participants and practitioners, and available financial resources. For ready-to-use co-creation solutions, take a look at TransformCity and Citizenlab.

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